

Accurate prediction on clopidogrel's abnormal behaviors and pharmacobehavioral economics

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Abstract

Thirteen years ago, under asymmetrical conditions, by analyzing the abnormal economic behavior and game process of clopidogrel after marketing, based on behavioral economics theory, we predicted that there were serious problems with the core data and results of the CAPRIE Phase III trial. Initially, we found that CAPRIE's sample size and statistical power were severely inadequate, and CAPRIE's results were incorrect. Unfortunately, statistical professors almost all believe that we should not doubt these results after the trial obtained $P < 0.05$ results. Three years later, direct evidence was uncovered in Table 6 of the CAPRIE trial. Vital data on fatal events in many groups were lopsided and illogical (e.g. (i) The fatal events between the first and second subgroup, Clopidogrel, No. 1: No. 2 = 308 : 302; aspirin, No. 1 : No. 2 = 321 : 314; (ii) The data of fatal events between the fourth and fifth subgroup were unbalanced or wrong (Clopidogrel, No.4 Subgroup: No.5 Subgroup=490:560; aspirin, No.4 Subgroup: No.5 Subgroup = 487: 571). (iii) The nyrs in all of the subgroups were unbalanced or illogical]. The CAPRIE results were wrong, and clopidogrel couldn't be superior to aspirin. Wrong data, noise trading, companion effect, herd behavior, butterfly effect, etc. have led Clopidogrel's global sales to exceed \$90 billion. We propose to modify the guidelines for the administration of clopidogrel, revise the theory of medical statistics, and construct new disciplines such as

pharmacobehavioral economics, medical behavioral economics, and health behavioral economics, etc. Although our empirical study revealed negative information, we found that only a few drugs caused changes in medical behavior, resulting in economic growth of more than \$826.5 billion.

Keywords: Behavioral economics · Game theory · Pharmacobehavioral economics · Clopidogrel · Aspirin · Medical statistics · Clinical behavioral economics · Health behavioral economics · Medical behavioral economics · Prospect theory

Abstract

Objective: Thirteen years ago, under asymmetrical conditions, by analyzing abnormal economic behavior and game processes, etc. of antiplatelet clopidogrel after its launch, based on behavioral economics theory, we predicted that there were serious problems with the core data and the results of Phase III CAPRIE trial. At first, we found that CAPRIE's sample size and statistical power were severely inadequate, and CAPRIE's results were wrong. Unfortunately, statistical professors almost all believe that we should not doubt these results after the trial obtained $P < 0.05$ results.

Methods: We investigated the reliability and credibility of relevant core CAPRIE trial data by philosophy, logistics and medical statistics, etc.

Results: Three years later, direct evidence was found in Table 6 of the CAPRIE trial. The vital data for fatal events in many groups or subgroups were unbalanced, erroneous and illogical (e.g. (i) fatal events between the first and second subgroups, Clopidogrel, No. 1: No. 2 =308 : 302; aspirin, No. 1 : No. 2 =321 : 314). (ii) The data of fatal events between the fourth and fifth subgroup were unbalanced or wrong (Clopidogrel, No.4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup=490:560; aspirin, No.4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup = 487: 571). (iii) The nyrs in all of the subgroups were unbalanced or illogical (E.g. The nyrs between the first and second subgroups, Clopidogrel, No. 1: No. 2 =17,636 : 17,594; Aspirin, No. 1: No. 2 = 17,519: 17,482). (iv) The data of the nyrs between the fourth and fifth subgroups were unbalanced or illogical.

[Clopidogrel (nyrs), No.4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup=17,622:18,377; aspirin (nyrs), No. 4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup=17,501:18,354].

Conclusions: The CAPRIE study results were distorted or erroneous and illogical, and clopidogrel could not be better than aspirin. Statistically significant ($p=0.043$) relative risk reduction of 8.7% in favour of clopidogrel (95% CI: 0.3-16.5) came from incorrect data. Wrong data, noise trading, companion effect, herd behavior, butterfly effect, etc. have led Clopidogrel's global total sales to exceed \$92 billion. We suggested modifying clopidogrel administration guidelines to reduce high expenditure on medical treatment, and revising medical statistical theory based on poor sample size and statistical power. Although our empirical studies have revealed the economic phenomenon of obtaining huge profits by means of negative information, only through the behavioral changes of several drugs can it be found that economic growth involved in the theories of pharmacobehavioral economics etc. has increased by more than 826.5 billion USD. Therefore, we suggest that new disciplines such as pharmacobehavioral economics, medical behavioral economics, and health behavioral economics etc. should be established.

Keywords: Behavioral economics · Game theory · Pharmacobehavioral economics · Clopidogrel · Aspirin · Medical statistics · Clinical behavioral economics · Health behavioral economics · Medical behavioral economics · Prospect theory

1 Introduction

The clinical trial data of some drugs have always been hot topics [1]. In the past ten decade or so, we also have been focusing on the clinical trial results of some drugs with abnormal economic behaviors. In 2008, we found serious abnormal economic behaviors for clopidogrel. As a blockbuster drug, the global annual sale of clopidogrel achieved 5.9 billion USD in 2005 [2]. It is not until November 17, 2011 that Plavix will not be protected by patent [3], but Apotex Inc. applied to FDA for a generic clopidogrel in 2001 which was launched in 2006 successfully [2]. Then both Sanofi-Aventis and Bristol-Myers reached an agreement with Apotex that the two companies would pay Apotex at least \$40 million so that Apotex would postpone clopidogrel's launch to 2011 (Table 1) [3,4].

Table 1 Events playback	
Date	Events
Nov.2001	Apotex filed an abbreviated New Drug Application ("ANDA") with the FDA seeking approval to manufacture and sell a generic form of the active ingredient in Plavix® before the expiration of the 4,847,265 patent in November 2011 [3].
Mar. 2002	Sanofi-Synthelabo and Bristol-Myers Squibb (BMS) sued Apotex for infringing the Orange Book-listed patent, U.S. Patent No. 4,847,265, thereby initiating an automatic 30-month stay of FDA approval of Apotex's ANDA [4].
Jan. 2006	FDA granted final approval to Apotex's ANDA clopidogrel [5].
Mar. 2006	BMS, Sanofi and Apotex executed the first Plavix patent settlement agreement ("March Agreement").The two companies agreed to pay off Apotex a minimum of \$40million to hold off launching a generic version of Plavix until 2011 [6,7].
June30 2006	Apotex reported that it had reached an oral agreement with Defendant whereby Defendant agreed that it would not launch an authorized generic version of Plavix® during the license period granted to Apotex under the Revised Agreement [3].
Aug.8 2006	Apotex launched its generic clopidogrel bisulfate product at risk [4,8].

Aug.14 2006	Sanofi-aventis and BMS filed for a preliminary injunction in a US district court, seeking to stop Apotex from selling its generic version of Plavix [9].
Aug.31 2006	U.S. District Court for the Southern District of New York has granted a preliminary injunction ordering Apotex to halt its sales of a generic clopidogrel that competes with PLAVIX®. The Court denied Sanofi's request for a recall that was already sold [9].
June19 2007	The Court upheld the validity and enforceability of U.S. patent 4,847,265 covering clopidogrel, the active ingredient in Plavix®, maintaining the patent protection in the U.S.A until November 2011 [2,10].

2 Methods

2.1. Analysis of behavioral economics and game theory

From the perspective of behavioral economics and game theory [11-19], Apotex exhibited overconfident and risk-seeking behavior in seeking profits before clopidogrel's patent expired, while the patent holder exhibited risk aversion and under-reaction. An extremely high expected interest is exposed to the game's behavior under incomplete and asymmetrical information. We are deeply suspicious of the abnormal economic behavior – prisoner's dilemmas, chicken game and reciprocal altruism – displayed by the three companies in their handling of the launch of a generic version of clopidogrel [20-25]. We assumed if loopholes did exist in clopidogrel's U.S. patent 4,847,265 document to make it invalid and unable to protect the essential compound, and because the patent document has been published, then theoretically any pharmaceutical corporation can identify and utilize the patent loopholes to produce the generic drug due to its enormous benefits, which would be launched in the USA after the submission of ANDA to FDA. But that wasn't the case. Conversely, on May 17, 2012 [26], six months after the clopidogrel's patent expired, generic versions of clopidogrel from nine companies were approved by the FDA on the same day.

Clopidogrel, whose patent game began in 2001[3], has achieved effective market protection and best-in-class benefits beyond patent expectations, showing rare results

with approximately complete information. Given the poor sample size in the CAPRIE trial [27], we therefore suspect that there must be serious problems with the clinical trial results.

2.2. Product life cycle analysis [27]

Analyzed from product life cycle [28], clopidogrel was introduced as a new drug in 1998 while aspirin was an older one, and the costly Phase III CAPRIE trial finished in 1996 proved that clopidogrel was more effective than aspirin [29]. Furthermore, the conventional thinking patterns and business activities should be as follows: the following Phase IV trials should prove that clopidogrel (C) was more effective and securer than aspirin (A) under various circumstances or that C+A was more effective than clopidogrel [27], so as to achieve a longer product life cycle and bigger commercial profits, not that the C+A was highlighted more effective than aspirin. In fact, however, no large post-marketing trial has ever been conducted to compare clopidogrel with aspirin after its launch. As of May 2012, when clopidogrel's patent protection period expired, only one MATCH trial was conducted to investigate whether C+A was more effective than clopidogrel [30], but its results were negative. Large post-marketing trials such as CURE [31], CREDO and CHRAMA [32,33], after clopidogrel's launch were promising to prove C+A was more effective than aspirin and then in 2006, however, the weight ratio of aspirin to clopidogrel mostly exceeded 1:1 in the drug combination group, although aspirin had serious side-effects that had been mentioned in CAPRIE's background. In 2005, C+A was named a sweeping partner in cardiology [34]. And, in the CURE trial, patients started to be enrolled in December 1998, when Plavix was just launched.

Clopidogrel after being put into the market, it was designed to be used in combination with aspirin in clinical medicine, which was like looking for a big bird to fly together. From the point of view of the post-marketing process, there was a consistent and effective optimal model for clopidogrel's drug life cycle, which is the cultural marketing model of rapid growth driven by large-scale clinical trials of clopidogrel co-administration or 'big birds flying together' or the companion effect.

2.3. Medical statistics analysis

These abnormal behaviors shift our focus to the clinical trials that prompted the launch of clopidogrel to identify problems within them. In the previous study [27], we found that both the sample size and the statistical power were severely inadequate, and the results of the Phase III CAPRIE trial were not reliable enough to demonstrate that clopidogrel was more effective than aspirin. However, many medical statisticians believed that since the study had shown statistically significant differences between the two groups and "fortunately" achieved positive results, there was no need to further study the sample size and statistical power and doubted CAPRIE's results because the small probability event had occurred. Clearly, medical statisticians do not believe that the theory of medical statistics is wrong.

Even so, because doubts about clopidogrel's abnormal behavior have not been resolved since its inception, we have to evade the discussion of biostatistics theories based on sample size and statistical power. Because of the trust in behavioral economics and its prospect theory, we have been trying to look for more direct and simpler proofs to justify our judgment and to modify the statistical results when the P value is below 0.05 and the sample size and statistical power are insufficient.

Surprisingly, two years later, when focusing on the core data in the randomized, double-blind, parallel-group CAPRIE trial and re-analyzing and calculating its clinical endpoints (Figure 1), we found that big mistakes and incredible irrationality existed in the CAPRIE study results through basic logic principles and uncomplicated statistical analysis [35].

We want to make complex issues clear through concise language and clear logical approaches.

3 Results

Table 6 of the CAPRIE study included primary and secondary outcome clusters. However, data on fatal events in first outcome events were unbalanced and illogical as follows (Figure 1).

3.1. Data on fatal events and the nyrs in the fourth and fifth subgroups were unbalanced and illogical.

For fatal events among the first outcome events, the fifth subgroup had only one frequency of "death from any cause," while the fourth subgroup had three frequencies of "any stroke, MI, or death from any cause". Moreover, in the comparison of two-sample parallel design, the first outcome events of "death from any cause" in any clopidogrel group or any aspirin group may have only one number. The total number of fatal figures in the fourth subgroup should be greater than those in the fifth subgroup, and the number of clopidogrel (nyrs) (nyrs: Patient-years at risk for outcome cluster) or aspirin (nyrs) in the fourth subgroup should be bigger than those in the fifth subgroup, respectively, but these were not the case.

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Outcome event cluster and treatment group	First outcome events			Event rate per year	Relative-risk reduction (95% CI)	p
	Non-fatal	Fatal	Total			
Ischaemic stroke, MI, or vascular death (primary cluster)						
Clopidogrel (nyrs=17636*)	631	308	939	5.32%	8.7% (0.3 to 16.5)	0.043
Aspirin (nyrs=17519) No.1 Subgroup	700	321	1021	5.83%		
Ischaemic stroke, MI, amputation, or vascular death						
Clopidogrel (nyrs=17594)	677	302	979	5.56%	7.6% (-0.8 to 15.3)	0.076
Aspirin (nyrs=17482) No.2 Subgroup	737	314	1051	6.01%		
Vascular death						
Clopidogrel (nyrs=17482)	..	350	350	1.90%	7.6% (-6.9 to 20.1)	0.29
Aspirin (nyrs=18354) No.3 Subgroup	..	378	378	2.06%		
Any † stroke, MI, or death from any cause						
Clopidogrel (nyrs=17622)	643	490	1133	6.43%	7.0% (-0.9 to 14.2)	0.081
Aspirin (nyrs=17501) No.4 Subgroup	720	487	1207	6.90%		
Death from any cause						
Clopidogrel (nyrs=18377)	..	560	560	3.05%	2.2% (-9.9 to 12.9)	0.71
Aspirin (nyrs=18354) No.5 Subgroup	..	571	571	3.11%		

*Patient-years at risk for outcome cluster; †Includes primary intracranial hemorrhage; MI=myocardial infarction.

Table 6: Intention-to-treat analysis - primary and secondary outcome clusters

Fig. 1 Table 6 in the CAPRIE trial.

In Table 6 of CAPRIE, fatal events data for the fourth and fifth subgroups (Clopidogrel, No.4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup=490:560; Aspirin, No. 4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup=487:571) [35], nyr data between the fourth and fifth subgroups [Clopidogrel, No.4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup=17,622:18,377; Aspirin, No. 4 Subgroup: No. 5 Subgroup=17,501:18,354] were unbalanced or incorrect.

3.2. The data for fatal events and nyrs in the second and third subgroups are imbalanced and illogical.

For fatal events among the first outcome events, the third subgroup included only one frequency of vascular death at first occurrence, while the second subgroup

included four frequencies of vascular death, ischaemic stroke, MI, and amputation. **The total number of fatal figures in the second subgroup should be bigger than those in the third subgroup, and the number of aspirin (nyrs) in the second subgroup should be greater than those in the third subgroup, but this was not the case either.**

In Table 6 of CAPRIE, fatal events data for the second and third subgroups (Clopidogrel, No.2: No.3 Subgroup=302:350; aspirin, No.2: No.3 Subgroup=314:378) [35], and nyr data between the second and third subgroups (Aspirin, No.2: No.3 Subgroup =17,482:18,354) were unbalanced or wrong.

3.3. The data for fatal events and nyrs in the first and second subgroups are confusing and illogical.

For fatal events among first outcome events, the first subgroup included only three frequencies of vascular death, ischaemic stroke and MI at first occurrence in primary cluster events, while the second subgroup included four frequencies of vascular death, ischaemic stroke, MI and amputation at first occurrence in both primary and secondary events. **The total number of fatal events in the second subgroup should be greater than those in the first subgroup, respectively, and the figure of clopidogrel (nyrs) or aspirin (nyrs) in the second subgroup should be bigger than those in the first subgroup.** The truth, however, is the reverse of these.

In Table 6 of CAPRIE, fatal events data for the first and second subgroups (Clopidogrel, No.1: No.2 Subgroup =308:302; Aspirin, No.1: No.2 Subgroup =321:314) [35], and nyr data between the first and second subgroups (Clopidogrel, No.1: No.2 Subgroup =17,636: 17,594; aspirin, No.1: No.2 Subgroup =17,519:17,482) was unbalanced or wrong.

There were many more perversions and violations of normal logic, which will not be listed in this paper one by one. Clearly, the conclusion that clopidogrel was more effective than aspirin came from incorrect data. A similar study---the data in Table 3 in the Dutch TIA Trials – highlighted more disorder of the data from the CAPRIE [36].

3.4. The nyrs in all subgroups were confused and illogical.

Table 2 Nyrs adjusted by difference value in the CAPRIE trial								
	No.1		No.2		No.4		No.5	
	Subgroup		Subgroup		Subgroup		Subgroup	
Drug	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A
Sample size	9,599	9,586	9,599	9,586	9,599	9,586	9,599	9,586
DV Nyrs	117		112		121		23	
Nyrs	17,636	17,519	17,594	17,482	17,622	17,501	18,377	18,354
ADV Nyrs	86,391	86,274	82,699	82,587	89,344	89,223	16,982	16,959

C =clopidogrel; A=aspirin;

DV Nyrs= Difference Value of Nyrs of clopidogrel and aspirin in same subgroup;

ADV Nyrs =Adjust Nyrs by Difference Value = (No.XC- No.XA)/(9599-9586) = DV Nyrs/(9599-9586).

With the exception of the third subgroup, the other four subgroups in CAPRIE Table 6 had higher numbers of nyrs and per capita nyrs in Group C than in Group A (Table 2; Figure 1). It seems that aspirin is superior to clopidogrel. In all subgroups, clopidogrel or aspirin group nyrs were lower than their ADV Nyrs, which was illogical.

4 Conclusions and discussion

4.1. Nyrs in the CAPRIE

Extremely elusively, nyrs is the key reason in the CAPRIE trial of misleading or transferring reader' attention, or arising confused thoughts. Many people, including doctors, even some have raised the same question of "how to explain the problem that diverse nyrs in various subgroups lead to unlikely results?"

Different nyrs in different subgroups create such plausible environments that it is difficult to discover the truth. Because of this, we suffered for a long time without finding a real breakthrough on the issues, even though we knew they existed in CAPRIE and kept focusing on them.

4.1.1 It is an objective fact that in CAPRIE with two-sample parallel design, the event number of any disease (with the same definition), regardless of which subgroup it belongs to, will increase by one statistical datum, not by two or three different data. For example, for any disease such as ischemic stroke, MI or vascular death, **no matter how many nyrs in a subgroup is, the total number of disease events in a CAPRIE trial with two-sample parallel design for the same drug**, even if recorded in two, three or four different subgroups, will certainly be the same statistical datum in any subgroup. Otherwise, this would imply that the total number of events for this disease has not been recorded, or that it has overtaken the record in another subgroup of the CAPRIE, which is not consistent with the facts.

4.1.2. As for "fatal events among first outcome events for death from any cause" (FEFOEDA) , the definition of which is specific in the CAPRIE, because the number of patients in the clopidogrel and aspirin groups of the whole trial is fixed, no matter how many person-times in its subgroup are under statistical analysis, the number of FEFOEDA in the CAPRIE will be one datum for any drug, whether in the fourth or fifth subgroup. In other words, for the number of "fatal events among first outcome events of 'death from any cause'" in C-group or A-group, if the statistical data in one subgroup is different from that in another subgroup, it must be lost or increased in one of the subgroups. Since no one can answer what the number of "the data of FEFOEDA " in CAPRIE is, the data is obviously wrong. Accordingly, if the number of "FEFOEDA" in Group C in the fifth subgroup is 560, then in the fourth subgroup it should be more than **560, not 490**.

How to produce two different numbers for the events of the same disease – FEFOEDA in the same one CAPRIE trial? When its definition is specific and the same in CAPRIE.

More importantly, the numbers of nyrs in the fourth subgroup, which should be larger than those in the fifth subgroup, are now incorrect or spurious.

4.1.3 Similarly, the number of "fatal events among first outcome events for vascular death" (FEFOEVA), regardless of clopidogrel or aspirin group in any subgroup, has only one datum, respectively, in the CAPRIE. If the numbers of

FEFOEVA in clopidogrel and aspirin groups in the third subgroup are 350 and 378, respectively, they should undoubtedly be the same amount in the second subgroup. However, in fact, the number of FEFOEVA in the second subgroup is unexpectedly lower than in the third subgroup, even though the second subgroup contains the number of other events such as ischemic stroke, MI and amputation, and more illogical, the person-time in the second subgroup **17,594** is, on the contrary, lower than that in the third subgroup **18,354** in Table 6. As a result, the data in these two subgroups are unbalanced by comparison, which is also beyond reason or error.

4.1.4 In the CAPRIE trial, the sample sizes of the clopidogrel and aspirin groups were 9,599 and 9,586, respectively, and there were 13 more subjects in group C. From the analysis of the difference in number of nyrs, the total number of nyrs occurring in 13 subjects in the first subgroup should be $17,636 - 17,519 = 117$, and the average number of nyrs per person in the first subgroup should be $117/13 = 9$. If the above logic is true, the total number of nyrs in the C-group in the first subgroup should be about $9,599 \times 9 = \mathbf{86,391}$, not **17,636**, and the same for other subgroups (Table 2).

Therefore, $P=0.043$ and the overall relative-risk reduction of 8.7% in favor of clopidogrel in CAPRIE were all wrong, illogical, and non-evidence-based medicine (non-EBM).

4.2. Modifying statistical theory based on sample size and power, clopidogrel's treatment guidelines

Our past study has demonstrated the limitations of sample size and statistical power, as well as the unreliability of CAPRIE [27]. In the first subgroup of Table 6, the total sum of sample size in both group C and group A was only **35,155** (**17,636+17,519**) even by annual prevalence rate (Figure.1), but by the approaches mentioned in the paper, sample size should be at least **84,968** in order to obtain statistically significant difference ($P=0.043$). Unfortunately, CAPRIE's unreliable results did not attract the attention of the FDA and the statistical and medical communities.

Nevertheless, this motivates us to reflect on the reliability and loopholes in the relevant medical statistical theory. Typically, the minimum sample size required for a

given statistical power must be calculated before a trial is designed,[37], but when statistically significant differences were generated, the back-stepping approach was ignored by many medical statisticians to calculate the insufficient sample size and poor statistical power, which resulted in unreliable results. Because they thought the trials had succeeded rather "fortunately". Guided by faulty statistical theoretical systems, strong anchoring psychology and framing effects are exposed when confronted with the conflict of breaking old theories [38].

In other words, as long as the P-value is below 0.05, there is a statistically significant difference between the two samples, even in the presence of erroneous or distorted data and insufficient sample size and statistical power below 0.75. It pointed to serious gaps in current statistical theory. That is, the current statistical approach could only infer the minimum sample size of a future trial in a given statistical power, but not the reliability of the results obtained in a given sample size. Therefore, we proposed to modify the medical statistical theory based on sample size and statistical power: when verifying sample size and statistical power for a finished trial whose results showed statistically significant differences, the conclusion that there is a significant difference between the two samples cannot be drawn when both insufficient sample size and statistical power are present below 0.75.

Obviously, the META analysis and pharmacoeconomics evaluation of clopidogrel based on CAPRIE's results were also unreliable [39-41]. Hereby, clopidogrel's treatment guidelines or consensus should be modified.

4.3. Building new disciplines, such as pharmacobehavioral economics

Three hypotheses: First, if there was no significant difference in clinical effects from aspirin in CAPRIE, clopidogrel could hardly have been approved by the FDA [42]. **Second**, if no one finds out and no journal is willing to publish CAPRIE's Phase III results are wrong, clopidogrel will continue to create miracles on the basis of huge accumulated sales. Meanwhile, clinicians may continue to misuse the drug. **Third**, without the theoretical guide originating from combination of behavioral economics and game theory and our firm confidence in its prospect theory [11-19,23-25,43], even if we found abnormal behavior of clopidogrel after it was launched, we could

never have insisted on studying its important processes and details before and after launch. In spite of the large asymmetry in medical information, finally, we found that CAPRIE results were wrong, and the noise trade, 'big bird flying together', companion effect and extensive effect of herd behavior existed in clinical use after launch [44-47]. We also discovered clopidogrel's secrets behind its great success and the abnormal behaviors of 'bad money driving out good money' [48,49].

Essentially, it is common for physicians to focus only on the main results in CAPRIE's Table 6, such as $P=0.043$, or relative risk reduction=8.7%, but rarely on other key data. Selective field deviation or selective field defects usually exist in daily life. We asked a number of doctors or professors who had prescribed clopidogrel how they interpreted the confounding fatal first outcome events in Table 6. No one, on the other hand, was not surprised. Even epidemiology and statistics professors were extremely shocked by the confusion and errors in the data in Table 6.

However, although most professionals were shocked after seeing the full data derivation process and admitted that the core data of the CAPRIE results were grossly erroneous, they did not believe that the CAPRIE results published in a well-known journal were wrong, which was probably our mistake. It seems that their cognition of the same thing appears at the same time as separation and division of thought. If we ask them why they see the problem this way, the answers are all the same – "How could the famous journal make such a big mistake?" The symptoms of 'famous medical journals effect' or treatment guidelines effect or source dependence or famous medical journal dependence or guideline dependence appeared among many people [50]. This may also be called the cognitive fallacy of split thinking or journal-dependent cognitive fallacy.

Unfortunately, even most professionals with advanced degrees still fall somewhere between rational and irrational when discussing the results of the CAPRIE. They believe in EBM but self-deny it (EBM Paradox), and they believe in data but deny logical new data, which leads to collective cognitive reduction. When they knew that CAPRIE's statistical data were highlighted with significant logical errors, they still trusted the results of previous studies (Evidence Paradox), showing a strong

anchoring bias and framing effect or negative feedback failure [39,51]. When they are aware of their obedience to authority, they are still unable to get rid of the psychological framework of blind adherence to authority, which leads to the collapse of effective decision-making.

Perhaps in their minds, famous journals represent the law of large numbers [52]. However, the discovery that we reversed CAPRIE's results is regarded as the law of small numbers under intuitive thinking in their subconscious, rather than based on strict logical thinking [53]. Their worship of EBM turned into blind worship of famous medical journals, so that they lost their basic logical thinking and lateral thinking. Perhaps the recency effect may not be sufficient to combat the primary effect [54,55], and the thunder effect or 'new clinical guideline effect' may be required.

In retrospect, clopidogrel's great success should be based on the wrong CAPRIE results and reinforced by a series of large post-marketing trials of drug combination and the following treatment guidelines. Between 1998 and 2006, five costly Phase IV trials to prove C+A was more effective than aspirin and seven large post-marketing trials of C+A combination were conducted [30-33,56-59]. The companion mode of C+A combination can better promote the 'big bird flying together'. Noise trading, 'P value <0.05', 'famous journal effect', herd behaviour, 'big bird flying together', and companion effect, etc. have increased clopidogrel from 1.279 billion euros in 2002 to \$9.4 billion in global sales in 2010, and to date, cumulative global sales have exceeded \$92 billion. Total consumption, including human resources or expenditures related to the clopidogrel industry, may have reached over \$300 billion. We can also recognize the huge butterfly effect caused by small changes in nyrs and fatal event data from a single subject [60,61]. However, the expensive cost of clopidogrel has led to soaring costs for patients and social security, which is contrary to the principles of health economics. It could be "bad money driving out good money." Therefore, we should review the results obtained from the pharmacoeconomics assessment of clopidogrel's cost-effectiveness or cost-effectiveness.

Most published research findings are false [62]. Before behavioral economics

was introduced to CAPRIE analysis, errors within CAPRIE were not discovered in previous META analyses, studies of pharmacoeconomics or health economics, and many reviews of clopidogrel [39-41], or by countless doctors who have prescribed clopidogrel. Therefore, new opportunities for the pharmaceutical industry may arise due to the combination of behavioral economics with pharmacoeconomics, pharmacy, medicine, health or hygiene.

The medical industry is a pillar industry and sunrise industry in today's society, with a global market value of more than \$3 trillion. It is weakly periodic, but the drug itself is generally periodic. With the discovery of drug action targets and the innovation of action mechanisms and theories for disease treatment, the introduction of new drugs can enhance people's health and create huge economic benefits for pharmaceutical companies. People's behaviors and motivations run through the entire process from development to drug launch, including preclinical studies, clinical studies, clinical use, drug evaluation, marketing, and more. In addition, with the continuous development of CAR-T and stem cell therapies [63-66], the clinical treatment behavior of doctors for certain diseases and the health care approach expected by the public are gradually changing, and new related industries are also forming.

John Nash, Nobel laureate in economics, once said that it takes more than 50 years for a great economic theory to verify its significance [67]. After we put forward the theories, we found that theories can be thoroughly and elaborately verified every day from drug development behavior or clinical behavior or preventive behavior, etc.

Although our previous empirical studies have revealed the economic phenomenon of obtaining huge profits through negative information, pharmacobehavioral economics or medical behavioral economics is more capable of showing or predicting the relationship between economic growth and changes in medical behavior in a passionate or rosy way. Since the 1980s, due to the superior lipid-regulating effect of statins and moderate adverse reactions, it has rapidly replaced fibrates as a research hotspot. In terms of clinical therapeutic behavior and interest in regulating blood lipids, many people have shifted from fibrates that inhibit acetyl CoA carboxylase

(TG synthetase) to statins that reduce intracellular cholesterol synthesis by competitively inhibiting the rate-limiting enzyme of endogenous cholesterol biosynthesis – HMG-CoA reductase. After the marketing of lovastatin, the clinical treatment behavior of hyperlipidemia has been significantly and remarkably changed. As of 2017, the cumulative annual sales of atorvastatin exceeded \$152.3 billion, ranking first in the world, and only cumulative annual sales of atorvastatin, rosuvastatin, and simvastatin have exceeded \$265.2 billion [68]. We believe that every 10-30 year cycle after the drug is on the market [69], there will definitely be some blood lipid regulating drugs with other mechanisms of action and changes in clinical behavior, with cumulative annual sales of more than \$30-150 billion, and PCSK9 inhibitors should not be excluded. Moreover, it can be seen that seemingly simple changes in medical behavior bring huge and uplifting economic benefits. When the glucocorticoid fluticasone and the long-acting β -receptor agonist--salmeterol were combined into a compound preparation-Seretide, it became the largest type of therapeutic combination in the inhaler market. Just because of changes in drug delivery behavior in the past, its cumulative sales have surprisingly exceeded \$100.2 billion [68]. Furthermore, due to the widespread presence of tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α) in inflammatory tissues and the lack of effective treatment for rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and ankylosing spondylitis, TNF- α is regarded as inflammatory targets. Therefore, pharmaceutical companies have developed multiple biological diseases modifying drugs with anti-TNF- α , resulting in changes in the treatment behavior of these diseases. Although these drugs may also fail, produce only partial responses, or cause serious adverse reactions, so far, the cumulative sales of etanercept, infliximab and adalimumab have exceeded \$300 billion.⁶⁸ However, the authors believe that the above-mentioned drugs are only phased substitutes, and new targeted therapeutic drugs will continue to be developed in the future, of which cumulative sales will exceed \$100 billion. Fourth, the substitution of asparagine with glycine and the addition of two arginine molecules to the molecular structure of insulin resulted in the enhancement of the alkalinity and pharmacokinetic behavioral changes in the product [68]. Since the clinical administration of insulin was changed from 3 - 4 times a day

to the world's first once-a-day insulin glargine, the huge clinical behavioral advantage of insulin glargine has made its cumulative sales exceed \$69.5 billion by 2017 [68]. It can be seen that we only cite a few drug cases and find that the economic growth involved in these theories (pharmacobehavioral economics, etc.) has exceeded \$826.5 billion. Returning to the COVID-19 pandemic, due to preventative behavior, an estimated 129 billion disposable masks and 65 billion gloves are used worldwide every month [70]. Although these wastes will cause extensive environmental pollution, they will inevitably bring lightning, huge and rolling economic benefits to the industry while protecting public health.

While uncovering the secrets of clopidogrel, we still feel the urgent need to establish new disciplines, such as pharmacobehavioral economics [35], medical behavioral economics or clinical behavioral economics or health behavioral economics or hygiene behavioral economics,^{1A-5A} in order to research, analyze, discover, explain, guide and predict drug development, production, clinical use and marketing, and study drugs from different perspectives to cultivate new economic growth points. In addition, from a new perspective, to study the interaction law between human behavior and medical and health economic activities, guide the formulation of medical and health policies, optimize the allocation and utilization of medical and health resources, improve the economic and social benefits of medical and health investment and services, and reduce the unnecessary burden of ordinary families and the whole society will be of great benefit to the healthy development of the pharmaceutical industry. We hope our findings will help families and society at large reduce transaction costs or overspending on medical treatments.

We do not understand why the results of clinical trials are so wrong. Although it is difficult to avoid mistakes in the operation of enterprises, it is still necessary for CRO companies to upgrade their management level.

^{1A} The definition of pharmacobehavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or

economic phenomena or economic planning or economic laws in drug R & D, investment, production, quality control, application, marketing, sales, supervision, management, vigilance, medical insurance, delisting and its whole life cycle, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote R&D, investment, production, clinical medication, supervision, marketing, medical insurance, and public policy formulation, etc.

^{2A} The definition of health behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic planning or economic laws in health, health care, prevention, medical treatment, health services, health management, health industry, health policy, health insurance, health investment, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote prevention, health care, treatment, health management, health insurance, and the formulation of public policies, etc.

^{3A} The definition of medical behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic planning or economic laws in medical treatment, prevention, nursing, medical insurance, medical management, medical decision-making, medical policy, or medical investment, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote prevention, treatment, medical insurance, and the formulation of public policies, etc.

^{4A} The definition of clinical behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic planning or economic laws in clinical diagnosis, clinical treatment, clinical medication, clinical effect, clinical equipment, clinical nursing, clinical management, clinical investment, medical insurance, etc on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote prevention, clinical treatment, medical

insurance, and the formulation of public policies, etc.

^{5A} The definition of hygiene behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, evaluating or solving economic problems or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic planning or economic laws in disinfection, hygiene, health, health care, prevention, medical treatment, hygiene services, hygiene management, hygiene industry, hygiene policy, hygiene investment, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote disinfection, prevention, health care, hygiene insurance, and the formulation of public policies, etc.

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Disclosure Statement

The Phase III CAPRIE trial, which has generated cumulative sales of clopidogrel in excess of \$90 billion, makes it easy to judge that almost all of the core data and results of the Phase III CAPRIE trial are illogical or erroneous, as long as five high-level experts with medical background, epidemiology and medical statistics background gather together to calculate and discuss relevant issues for 1 hour.

Although the authors are very worried that this kind of drug with seriously wrong clinical trial data may affect patients' health after it is widely used. From 2012 to 2022, although this paper was submitted to various journals many times, it was rejected, not because the views or demonstrations in this article were wrong. Many of them are not interested in this issue. We don't know if society still needs the Hippocratic Oath, medical ethics, and evidence-based medicine? This may require discussion by the U.S.FDA and SEC, as well as experts in economics, finance, management, medicine, pharmacy, medical statistics, ethics, etc. to discuss this issue. The Hippocratic Oath may need to be reconsidered in today's society.

It can be expected that the bubble caused by irrational exuberance will burst after the normalization of the negative feedback mechanism of market economy operation.

We don't know if society cares about the safety of patients who need anticoagulant? We do not know whether Western media society still attaches importance to justice and ethics? We do not know if there will be a well-known journal with medical ethics and justice to publish this article? This may overturn some economic theories and give economists another difficult subject. The author believes that an economic theorem that requires too many assumptions to be established does not seem to be a theorem anymore. The author designs a new economic system, which is the new negative feedback mechanism of market economy operation when the market and the government or regulation fail at the same time (Liu 2021), hoping to achieve normal results.

We also know that some journals may be under great pressure after receiving this article. It is unfair and inappropriate that only a small journal should bear the huge pressure. Life is not easy when the capital is king. We are even reluctant to bring a hot potato to the editor-in-chief and his colleagues. After being rejected, the paper often does not want to be submitted again.

The process of disclosing the illogical data and wrong results of the CAPRIE trial, which cannot be officially published so far, shows that absolute neoliberal economics should sometimes be just a fairly skilled method or methodology for high IQ individuals or interest groups to transfer wealth as much as possible under the banner of liberal economics, rather than a science (Liu 2021).

However, if a society does not have a common ethical code to follow, it is difficult to say that it is not a chaotic society or a divided society.

If a country does not have a common moral code to follow, it is difficult to say that it is not a chaotic country or a country that will not be divided in the future. If integrity and ethics are still a bit abstract, does this society need to be a bit compassionate?

We don't know if Earth still needs the Hippocratic Oath, medical ethics, and evidence-based medicine? We also know that your journal may be under a lot of pressure after receiving this article. It is unfair and inappropriate that only one periodical should be under enormous pressure. Life is not easy when the capital is king. We are reluctant even to bring a hot potato to the editor-in-chief and your colleagues. But it is difficult to say that a society is not chaotic or divided if it does not have a common ethical code to follow. If integrity and ethics are still a bit abstract, does this society need to be more compassionate? "If you are neutral in situations of injustice, you have chosen the side of the oppressor. If an elephant has its foot on the tail of a mouse and you say you are neutral, the mouse will not appreciate your neutrality". We very much hope that the medical world still has medical ethics and the Hippocratic Oath.

Predicting success is a joy, but more often than not, it's a pain. When there is a huge correlation between the prediction of success and the interests of interest groups, the predicted results can only be silent, even if the patient's clinical medication is

unreasonable. Many people in this society advocate that people with Western religious beliefs are trustworthy, but I haven't seen much of my article rejected in the past decade. On the contrary, when seeking the help of philosophy, history, and the Hippocratic oath over and over again, year after year, Hippocratic never appeared, but the author found that the chronicles of Europe, ancient Egypt, ancient Greece, and ancient Rome were forged by religious groups. Socrates, Plato, Shakespeare, and others are absolutely fictional characters, and many scientific and technological achievements in ancient Europe were copied from ancient China and then translated into original works by some European people in a different language.

When the author predicted in January 2020 that COVID-19 vaccine could not be infected by COVID-19 vaccine, and even if 90% of the world's population had been vaccinated with COVID-19 vaccine, herd immunization would not be possible, almost no one believed it. Seeing that a huge amount of money and energy in the world has been invested in the R&D and promotion of COVID-19 vaccine, it is like seeing the predictable results of future patients after vaccination and the waste of huge social wealth, and nameless pain emerges in my heart. Unhelpfully, the author proposed a second choice plan. If it is necessary to receive the vaccine, it is best to choose an appropriate vaccination time based on the actual situation and one's own circumstances, and try to delay the vaccination as much as possible by zoning and grading.

The world has received at least 12 billion doses of the COVID-19 vaccine over the past three years, but the final fact is that almost all people who received the COVID-19 vaccine have been infected with COVID-19, which could cost the world hundreds of billions of dollars.